

GENDER EQUALITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT EDUCATION OF GIRLS AND WOMEN

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Abstract:

Girls and women are equally capable of handling this world as compared to the men. But the typical mindset becomes an obstacle in accepting this fact. Women does not enjoy the same conditions in work place as men. They earn less money than men. I am sure that Kareena Kapoor –Khan must have earned less money than Arjun Kapoor in the film Ki and Ka. Even our film industry is not an exception in this context.

It is the concerned aspect of labour rights.

“Gender equality is more than a goal itself. It is a pre-condition for meeting the challenge of reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and promoting good governance. “ _Kofi Annan

Feminist aren't anti-men.

We are pro-human.

Men and women both are the parts of our society. Whether it is india or any other country, females are still to be accepted as equal to men in many contexts Right to education, Right to Speak and so on. As rightly said by the great socialist Savitribai Phule, “If one woman becomes educated, she can educate the entire family.” The reason behind this thought is kids spend more time with their mother as compared to the father. As father is mainly earns the money for the family, and he is also concerned as the head of the family in our society.

On the other side, mothers are the typical home-makers even if she is working or not working. She has to manage her home as well the office. The typical Indian scenario is, when both of them are back to home after a long tiring day, woman will rush into the kitchen to arrange the food for her family, irrespective of the family's financial status. Men will sit on the couch either with the TV remote control or with his cell phone.

This happens because of the typical mindset that the women are bound to take care of the kitchen. Especially, the mother- she never gets retired. Isn't it? Cooking and looking after everyone's food requirement is always in her mind. Father has to look after to all the financial matters. So, he needs to be more relaxed at home. People prefer money over family.

We need to understand that even the woman gets tired of her daily routine. She also needs a break. So , with this context, let us think in a different way to understand the concept of Ki and Ka.

Education of girls and women affects the economic advancement of the entire country. It helps to improve the lives of their families as well. The education helps the woman to become a confident human being by creating an awareness about their rights, about the various laws which are made for their welfare and about the world scenario.

Let us see, some of the Opportunities with regards to the Education of Girls and Women:

- A lifeline to development:
Among the children not attending the school, there are twice as many girls as boys. This ratio shows that, we need to work on this problem. Mid-day meals, free uniforms and books , scholarship facilities can be used as a medium to encourage the girls to complete their schooling education. If the base of their life is made strong by using education to make it concrete then it will help them to draw a strong lifeline to the development.
- Low cost of education and flexible time-tables:

Basic education should be cost free. Since, many girls are from financially weak background, they provide help in household activities and then they go to the school. Because of the family responsibilities the need flexible school time-tables. So they complete their schooling with minimum bunking.

- Parental and community involvement:

PTA meeting at the regular intervals can help to encourage the Education of girls and women. Various social issues like current affairs and the government policies can be discussed to enhance the awareness among the society with regards to the education of girls and women.

- Relevant curriculum:

If we educate the girls using local language, it becomes one of the plus points in motivating the girls to finish their schooling..The local language will help the other people also to take keen part in education process. It will definitely encourage others to join the school because the fear or hesitation of English language will no longer exist.

- Support group:

If we, as a society, start supporting the education of girls and women, it will become the world wide issue, heading towards the progress. Sometimes, political and economic arrangements of the government are not enough to reach the masses. So, foundations like UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), Shiksha Trust and many more like them are working as a moral and financial support to encourage the noble cause of education.

- Separate school for girls:

Some people hesitate to send their daughters to co-ed schools because of the religious issues. So to overcome this hesitation, we need to arrange the separate school to make them more comfortable.

Now, let us see, some of the Obstacles in Education of Girls and Women:

- Family background:

Sometimes, the un-educated parents does not take interest in educating the girl child. Since, the typical mindset is that, she will go away after the marriage. Then why to waste time and money on her education? Boy's education is preferred over girl's education. Boy is considered to be as the lightning lamp of the family. So, he needs to shine bright. Our society needs to rethink over this big issue.

- Health problem:

Early marriage, mal-nutrition, early motherhood, lack of hygiene are some of the health related problem, which are becoming the obstacles in education of girls and women.

- Culture and tradition:

Girls are meant to be an expert in kitchen, raising the kids and looking after the family members. The previous generation of women did the same. So the same things will be continued in future. This wrong mentality which has been labeled as the culture and tradition.

- Violence and Security:

The risk of attack on the girls school is a serious concern in many countries. So the parents prefer to keep the children at home for safety reasons. In conflict affected countries, education is not always accessible.

- Poor infrastructure:

Lack of wash-rooms, over- crowded classrooms are some of the reasons to become an obstacle in education of girls and women.

Conclusion:

Skye Carpenter (Jan 2016)

Equality (He for She)

Females and males are one in this world, Although that is not the belief that has been furlled. We are told that one gender is better than the other, It seems it's just one stereotype , one after another. Equality can become realized, if only we believe And take the initiative to take action and achieve. Why shouldn't men and women be treated as the same? To have equal rights and equal pay, That should really be our aim. Men , gender equality is your issue too, Although , u might not agree, I am afraid it is true. You should have the right to express your Emotions and be what you please. You should not be pulled back by stigma, But instead be who you are at ease. Instead of fighting, we should be pulling together, And make this journey a joint endeavor. We are of equal value if only we open our eyes, At the heart of change is where we become most wise, Now or never? If not us then who? The interest in this movement must come through. Equality is not a privilege but a human right, All genders on the spectrum should be able to shine bright.